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“A HERO OF VALOR AND A FIGHT”

A hero of Valor is a fighter and never a quitter.
A shining lighthouse of vigor that only grows brighter.
Someone who is not a worrier but rather a brave warrior.
With a strong heart and a gallant core.

There is a hero I look up to with elation,
He stands still, full of hope and admiration.
I lack insight into why heroes experience feelings of isolation.
Even the strongest can have a sense of evolution.

He loves his people, his nation,
A guardian spirit with a sense of protection.
Though many may forget the wars he fought,
Every lesson he taught was filled with devotion.

In times of adversity, he stands true,
His heart still beats strong for the red, white, and blue.
I have faith that he will thrive for many years.
For within him is fate, which calms all fears.

Let's pay tribute to the hero I most admire.
He serves as a liberation primer.
A hero who is constantly nurturing and caring for people, in particular.
Even when the battle is over, he remains a true warrior.